

Netherlands

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Netherlands, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report on the national higher education system and complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in national systems, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<http://www.eter-project.eu>) for the period 2011-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

According to Eurydice¹, the Netherlands has a higher education system that comprises two types of HEIs:

- Universities and Universities of applied sciences (Hogescholen) funded by the government, which are listed in the Higher Education and Research Act (WHW)
- Private-sector institutions that do not receive government funding. Their courses and the certificates they award to graduates are legally recognised after they have been approved by the Education Inspectorate and the Accreditation Organisation of the Netherlands and Flanders (NVAO) (only two are included in ETER))

HEIs listed in the Higher Education and Research Act (WHW) include:

- **Universities** (including the Open University and theological and humanist universities)
- **Universities of applied sciences** (also known as HBO institutions or *hogescholen*)

Universities focus on academic teaching and research. They provide initial degree programmes, carry out academic research, train researchers and design engineers and transfer knowledge for the benefit of the community. **Universities of applied sciences** (*hogescholen*) provide higher professional education. They contribute to the development of those occupations to which their teaching is geared and conduct design and development activities and research related to specific occupations. They provide associate degree programmes as well as bachelor's degree programmes and in some cases master's degree programmes, and transfer knowledge for the benefit of the community.

¹<https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/netherlands/types-higher-education-institutions>

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Table 1² below provides a quantitative overview of the main institutional characteristics by HEI type. Around half of all Universities (Universiteit) are public institutions and the other half is private, mostly government-dependent. Out of the 57 HEIs, 55 receive government funding. Independent of the institutional character, all Universities except for one³ have the right to award PhDs. Universities of applied sciences (Hogescholen), on the other hand, are mostly private-government dependent and do not award PhDs. They account for more than half of all HEIs in the Netherlands.

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2020

Category		N	Public	Private	Private government-dependent	PhD awarding
University (including The Open University)	Universiteit	20	12	1	7	19
University of applied sciences	Hogeschool	37	1	1	35	0
Total		57	13	2	38	19

Note: Numbers reflect inclusion in ETER

² The table only shows the HEIs included so far in ETER. Apart from these, several private educational institutions exist, with many of them also offering higher education programmes. According to the Accreditation Organisation of the Netherlands and Flanders (NVAO), there are 58 private institutions offering accredited higher education degrees.

³ The Transnational University Limburg (TUL), a joint Dutch-Flanders university working across borders, does not award PhD degrees as that is effectuated through the two universities that collaborate in the TUL.

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

Data on the HEI foundation year provide information on the history of the Dutch higher education and its evolution over time.

The oldest university in the Netherlands, Leiden University, dates back to 1575. As shown in Figure 1, the number of Universities increased steadily since the 1940s. Contrarily, Universities of applied sciences have been established more recently, with the first one being established in 1929. There also was one prominent period of expansion of the number of Universities of applied sciences in the 1980s, when several then vocational colleges received higher education status. This substantial increase led to an outnumbering of the number of Universities in the Netherlands.

Figure 1. Foundation year of HEIs by type

However, the figure above only displays organisations that were independent at the end of the reporting period, and it does not account for mergers and other demographic events. Many of the current HEIs, in particular Universities of applied sciences, in the Netherlands are the result of such mergers between existing institutions.

Students

In terms of the number of students enrolled, Universities account for 40% of the students, while Universities of applied sciences for the other 60%. Universities of applied sciences play a more significant role for students at the bachelor level than Universities, with almost 70% of all bachelor students attending Universities of applied sciences. However, around 90% of all master students are enrolled at Universities. Unlike the Universities, the Universities of applied sciences are also offering associate degrees (ISCED 5). As mentioned before, PhDs are only awarded by Universities.⁴

Figure 2. Students by level and type of HEI, 2020

Note: Total students includes ISCED 5-7.

Personnel

People are a core resource for HEIs, as their competences are essential for teaching, undertaking research and producing scientific output. In that respect, ETER provides a rich set of data moving beyond the information

⁴ There are several types of PhD students, with some of them being students with scholarships, others being students without scholarships, and yet others being employed as junior staff in the university (with an employment contract). The data for PhD students shown in the graph refer to PhD candidates employed by Universities.

available in EUROSTAT, which allows to analyse the composition of personnel by type of HEI and characteristics such as gender, nationality, educational field and, from 2020 onwards, levels of seniority.

As shown in Figure 3, most of total personnel (measured in full time equivalents, FTE) is employed in Universities. Examining the personnel composition, this is mainly caused by the large variation in research and teaching assistants (RTAs). As only Universities are allowed to award PhDs, they are the only ones employing RTAs.

Figure 3. Personnel (FTE) by category and type of HEI, 2020

Since the data collection 2020, ETER also includes information on academic staff seniority level based on a classification jointly developed by OECD and EUROSTAT⁵. Combined with information on gender, this information allows measuring two critical issues, i.e. career prospects of academic staff and the so-called leaky pipeline, i.e. the fact that the share of female academic staff decreases systematically with seniority levels.

Data for Netherlands referring to seniority are available only for the Universities. Figure 4 presents the data measured in head counts (HC).⁶ Interestingly, the absolute number of academic personnel is largest at the junior level. Figure 4 also provides support for the notion of the leaky pipeline. While at the junior level the distribution of men and women is fairly balanced (52% male), at the senior level female staff is clearly underrepresented (28% female).

⁵ OECD (2022), Education at a Glance, Paris, pp. 412-413.

⁶ Using HC may underestimate the true gender imbalances (in full time equivalents, FTE) as the percentage of employees working part time is higher among women than among men. However, data is only available in HC.

Figure 4. Academic personnel by seniority level and gender in head counts (HC), 2020

Note: Data refer to Universities. Data on female staff broken down by seniority is missing for Universities of applied sciences

A final important dimension is the personnel's nationality since it is generally considered as beneficial for the quality of research to have an international staff. In ETER, this is measured by the share of academic personnel not having the citizenship of the country ('foreigners'). As shown in Figure 5 for the year 2020, Dutch Universities are characterized by a high share of international employees with around 40% of foreign academic personnel. This share has increased since 2013 by around 6 percentage points.

Figure 5. Share of foreign academic personnel (HC) by type of HEI, 2013 and 2020

Financial resources

As illustrated in Figure 6, in the year 2020, Universities accounted for more than 60% of total revenues of the entire HE sector and for a little less than 50% of total academic personnel (excluding research and teaching assistants) of the whole HEI system. This broadly corresponds to the fact that Universities also have an important research function. This difference is also reflected in the composition of revenues (see Figure 7), where Universities receive a substantial proportion of revenues from (research-related) third-party funds. Overall, the recurrent revenues received from the state (core budget) is the dominant revenue source for all institutional types in the Netherlands accounting for 59% of total resources for Universities and for 74% for Universities of applied sciences. Student fees play a less important role but are of higher relevance than in most other European countries. While approximately 10% of overall resources are derived from student fees in Universities, this number accounts for around 19% in Universities of applied sciences.

Figure 6. Resources, academic personnel and total students enrolled by type of HEI, 2020

Figure 7. Composition of resources by type of HEI, 2020

Changing roles over time

Figure 8 shows a pattern of slight increase in the number of enrolled students (ISCED 5-7) rising from around 670,000 students in 2011 to approximately 820,000 students in 2020 (+23%). The growth was slightly larger for Universities for which the number of students increased by a total of around 84,000 students (+34%), whereas the growth in Universities of applied sciences accounts around 68,000 students (+16%) between 2011 and 2020.

Figure 8. Students (ISCED 5-7) enrolled by type of HEI, 2011-2020

Note: Data for the Open University is missing.

As shown in Figure 9, the number of academic personnel (FTE) in Dutch HEIs slightly increased between 2011 and 2020 from around 43,000 academic staff to around 54,500 (+27%). While Universities increased the total academic personnel by around 6,300 employees (+25%), Universities of applied sciences employed around 5,200 more academic staff (+28%).

Figure 9. Academic personnel (FTE) by type of HEI, 2011-2020

Note: Includes research and teaching assistants in 2020 for Universities

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